

LASER IN ORTHODONTICS: A REVIEW

ABSTRACT

Laser technology has extended its reach to various fields of dentistry since its introduction. Being a non-invasive technique, its applications in orthodontics include enamel etching, bracket debonding, pain control, and accelerating tooth movement. The advantages of laser include improved hemostasis, reduced pain and inflammation, faster wound healing, and precise incision control. However, safety precautions must be considered in preventing possible tissue damage when using lasers.

Key words : Laser, Orthodontics

INTRODUCTION

The acronym LASER stands for "Light Amplification by Stimulated Emission of Radiation". A laser produces light by transforming electrical energy into optical energy. To generate laser light, atoms must be excited to a higher energy level and release their energy in phase. It is a nearly parallel, monochromatic, and coherent beam of light, which is opposite to ordinary lights¹. Generally, lasers are composed of three principal parts: An energy source, an active medium, and a set of two or more mirrors that form a resonator. The active medium can be a gas, crystal, or solid-state conductor which determines the wavelength of the laser. Laser light is produced as a result of the stimulation of the active medium with an external agent like a flash lamp strobe device, an electrical current, or an electrical coil². A laser beam has several physical characteristics that distinguish it from a typical white light source including collimation, coherence (phase correlation), and monochromaticity (single wavelength).

HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

In 1917, Einstein published an article on the quantum theory of radiation which is considered to be the basic concept of laser technology³. In 1960, Maiman built the first working laser with ruby as the active medium material⁴. Goldman introduced laser technique into the medical field and he reported the impact of ruby laser on dental caries in 1964. The results showed crater formation and dentine fusion along with disappearance of dental caries^{5, 6}. In 1964, Bell Laboratories developed the Neodymium doped yttrium Aluminum Garnet (Nd:YAG) laser and Carbon dioxide (CO₂) laser, researchers were able to extend laser technique to both hard and soft tissues in the oral cavity. Nd:YAG which remain the most widely used lasers in medicine⁷. In 1980, Nd:YAG laser was first reported to be used in dental caries prevention by Yamamoto and Sato⁸. Myers and Myers allowed this technique to be widely used in general dentistry⁹.

TYPES OF DENTAL LASERS

Lasers applied in dentistry are named after the chemical elements, molecules or compounds that compose the active medium which is stimulated. There are six basic types of lasers now are used in dentistry.

Table1. Types of Dental lasers⁷

NAME	ACTIVE MEDIUM	WAVE LENGTH	CHARACTER	APPLICATION
CO2 Laser	Gas-active, CO2	10600nm	Well absorbed by water; Highest absorption in hydroxyapatite; Non-contact mode	Soft tissue surgery; Enamel surface modification
Nd:YAG Laser	Solid active, crystal of yttrium aluminum garnet doped with neodymium	1064nm	Absorbed by water and pigment tissue(hemoglobin); Good hemostatic ability; Slightly absorbed by dental hard tissue Contact mode	Soft tissue surgery; sulcular debridement and remove surface carious lesion
Diode Laser	Solid active, solidstate semiconductor: aluminum, gallium and arsenide	800-980nm	Well absorbed by pigment tissue and water; Poorly absorbed by dental hard tissue; Contact mode with small size instrument	Soft tissue surgery; sulcular debridement
Argon Laser	Gas active, Argon	488nm; 514nm	488nm active camphoroquinone; 514nm absorbed by red pigment tissue; Poorly absorbed by dental hard tissue	Light curing dental materials; Sulcular debridement and highly vascularized lesions Caries detection
Er, Cr: YSGG and Er: YAG Laser	Er,Cr:YSGG : solid active, crystal of yttrium-scandiumgallium-garnet doped with erbium and chromium Er: YAG: solid active, crystal of yttrium gallium-garnet doped with erbium	Er, Cr: YSGG 2790nm Er: YAG 2940nm	Highest absorption in water; high affinity for hydroxyapatite	Caries removal and tooth preparation; Soft tissue surgery
Ho: YAG Laser	Solid active, crystal of yttrium aluminium garnet doped with holmium	2120nm	Absorption by water; Poorly absorbed by pigment tissue and dental hard tissue	Soft tissue surgery

CLASSIFICATION OF LASERS

Table 2: Classification of lasers based on their clinical uses¹⁰

LASER TYPE	WAVELENGTH	MAIN CURRENT CLINICAL USES
Argon	488, 514.5 nm	Curing, soft tissue desensitization
Diode	800-830, 950-1010 nm	Soft tissue, periodontics
Nd: YAG	1064 nm	Soft tissue, periodontics, Desensitization, Analgesia, Tooth whitening, and Endodontics
Er: YSGG	2.79 μm	Hard tissue
Er: YAG	2.94 μm	Hard tissue
CO₂	10.6 μm	Soft tissue, desensitization

Nd: YAG: Neodymium: yttrium-aluminium-garnet, Er: YSGG: Erbium doped yttrium scandium gallium garnet

APPLICATION OF LASER IN ORTHODONTICS

Enamel Etching

Laser etching was introduced into orthodontic bonding in the 1990s. Application of laser to an enamel surface causes localized melting and ablation and, therefore, removing enamel with numerous pores and bubble-like inclusions¹¹. This process is similar to the type III etching pattern produced by orthophosphoric acid². Laser irradiation, causes surface roughening and irregularity similar to that of acid-etching to a depth of 10-20 μm , depending on the type of laser and the energy applied to the surface. Laser etching of enamel and dentin has been reported to produce fractured, uneven surface and open dentin tubules, which is ideal for adhesion¹². The acid-resistant effect of laser etching is superior to phosphoric acid. Aside from the bond strength, laser etching is useful when applied in immediate bonding on surgically exposed teeth without acid etching¹³. Kim et al¹⁴ reported an in vitro study, where enamel was treated by Er: YAG laser and found to be more resistant to acid, than that treated by conventional acid etching. Hamamci, et al¹⁵ found less microleakage of brackets bonded by etching with Er: YAG and Er, Cr: YAG lasers than acid etching. Noel et al¹⁶ studied the acid-resistant effect induced by Argon laser. Lee et al¹⁷ compared the bond strength of orthodontic brackets after three different etching procedures: Acid etching, Er: YAG laser etching, and combining these two methods. Based on their results, the authors demonstrated that Er: YAG lasers may be an effective alternative to conventional acid etching. Even though laser etching has many advantages over conventional methods, it is not yet a routine procedure adopted in orthodontic bonding.

Compared to acid etching, the unpredictable bonding results of laser are probably one reason that has slowed the acceptance of laser etching in orthodontics.

Debonding of Bracket

The risk of enamel damage is a major concern of brackets debonding in orthodontics. The occurrence of enamel fracture is relatively higher with ceramic brackets because of the high bond strength^{18,19}. Laser irradiation can soften the composite resin by heating the brackets, help reducing the force required for debonding. The mechanism of laser debonding includes: thermal softening, thermal ablation or photoablation. When laser with low power density irradiates the brackets until the resin softens. The brackets will slide off the tooth surface with gravity. Thermal ablation and photoablation vaporize the resin when its temperature is raised quickly by high power density lasers. The resulting bracket can be blown off the tooth surface^{20, 21}. Strobl et al.²² successfully debonded single crystal alumina (sapphire) and polycrystalline alumina orthodontic brackets with both Nd: YAG (1,060 nm) and CO₂ (10.6 μm) lasers.

Pain Control

Tooth movement is often associated with pain, especially within the first 7 days after force applied²³. Low-level laser therapy (LLL) has been shown to have analgesic effects in a variety of therapeutic procedures^{24,25}. LLL is a new technique and is defined as the laser treatment in which the energy output is low enough that the temperature of the applied area will not rise above body temperature²⁶. Many researchers have reported that Nd: YAG, He-Ne, and GaAlAs diode lasers have analgesic effects for reducing orthodontic pain. Tortamano et al.²⁷ concluded that LLL effectively controls pain caused by the application of the first archwire, but it does not affect the start of pain after the first archwire is placed and doesn't alter the foremost painful day. According to findings, LLL reduces the prevalence of pain after multi banding compared to a control group at 6 and 30 hours^{28,24} However some studies shows that LLL offers no significant pain reduction after separation or placement of archwires^{26,29}.

Tooth Movement

LLL was reported to be able to stimulate fibroblast and chondrocyte proliferation, collagen synthesis, nerve regeneration, wound healing, and bone regeneration^{30,31}. LLL can accelerate bone remodeling and cause changes in alveolar bone during tooth movement by increasing the number and proliferation of osteoblasts and osteoclasts and collagen deposition in both pressure and tension sites. Kawasaki³² showed a 1.3 fold more movement of rat teeth irradiated by laser after 12 days.

Cruz et al.³³ investigated for the first time the effects of LLLT on humans. For the 11 patients within the study, half the upper arch served as a control group, receiving mechanical activation of the canine teeth every 30 days. The opposite half received an equivalent mechanical activation but was also irradiated with a diode laser. The results of the study showed a significantly greater acceleration of canine retraction on the side treated with LLLT compared with the control. According to some authors, if a laser dose is too low it will not cause a biostimulating effect, whilst a higher dose can inhibit tooth movement³⁴.

Bone Regeneration after Expansion

Rapid maxillary expansion is one of the most commonly used methods for expansion in orthodontic therapy³⁵. Usually following expansion a retention period of 3 to 4 months is needed for bone regeneration and remodeling³⁶. Low-level lasers can accelerate the opening of the mid-palatal suture and improve bone regeneration during and after rapid maxillary expansion according to several studies³⁷⁻³⁹. It may be helpful in reducing the retention time and preventing relapse.

Reducing Enamel Decalcification

After bonding, the enamel becomes more susceptible to carries because of increased plaque accumulation around the attachments. This often leads to decalcification of the enamel or formation of white lesions and presents a major problem for orthodontic patients⁴⁰⁻⁴². Many studies showed that an argon laser can be used to prevent enamel decalcification by altering its crystalline structure⁴⁰. Kim et al¹⁴ showed that Er: YAG laser etching of the enamel also imparts greater resistance to acid attack compared with acid etching.

SOFT-TISSUE APPLICATIONS RELATED TO ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT

Gingival enlargements are common sequelae of orthodontic patients with poor oral hygiene. Soft-tissue lasers are used for gingival recontouring, exposure of unerupted and partially erupted teeth, removal of hypertrophic and inflamed tissues, frenectomies, miscellaneous tissue and treatment of aphthous lesions⁴³. Soft-tissue lasers also can be used for aesthetic contouring of the gingiva within the smile framework, establishing tooth proportionally before bracket placement, crown lengthening, treatment crown height asymmetry or contouring of gingival and interdental margins⁴⁴. Laser cause minimal tissue damage, provide hemorrhage control and can also reduce post-operative pain.

LASER SAFETY AND HARMFUL EFFECTS OF LASERS

According to the standards of American National Standards Institute and Occupational Safety and Health Administration, lasers are classified into four different classes based on potential danger, as follows ⁴⁵:

- Class I: These are low-powered lasers that are safe to view
- Class IIa: These are low-powered visible lasers. They do not cause damage unless one looks directly along the beam for longer than 1,000 s
- Class II: These are low-powered visible lasers. They are dangerous when viewed along the beam for longer than 0.25 s
- Class IIIa: These are medium-powered lasers that are not dangerous when viewed for less than 0.25s
- Class IIIb: These are medium-powered lasers that are dangerous when viewed directly along the beam for any length of time
- Class IV: These are dangerous high-powered lasers that can cause damage to the skin and eyes. Even the reflected or radiated beams are dangerous. It is necessary to take appropriate safety measures. Most of the lasers used for medical and dental purposes are in this category.

Lasers operating at non-visible wavelengths (ultraviolet and infrared) and reflection of laser light from various surfaces can even increase potential danger. Retinal damage caused by these lasers can result in blindness. Protective glasses must be worn by both the patient and the practitioner during laser therapy.

CONCLUSION

The laser has influenced many clinical orthodontic practises including biostimulation, laser etching with its ease of use. Although the potential hazards of laser should be taken into consideration and strict safety procedures must be carried out during the application of laser therapy.

REFERENCES

1. Gould RG. The LASER, Light Amplification by Stimulated Emission of Radiation. The Ann Arbor Conference on Optical Pumping, the University of Michigan, June 15 through June 18, 1959. pp. 128. 4.
2. Nalcaci R, Cokakoglu S. Lasers in orthodontics. Eur J Dent. 2013 Sep;07(S 01):S119-25.
3. Einstein A. Zur Quantum Theorie der Strahlung, Phys Z 1917;18, 121-128.

4. Maiman TH. Stimulated optical radiation in ruby. *Nature* 1960;187:493-4.
5. Goldman L, Blaney DJ, Kindel DJ Jr, Frankee EK. Effect of the laser beam on the skin, preliminary report. *J Invest Dermatol* 1963;40: 121-122.
6. Goldman L, Hornby P, Meyer R, Goldman B. Impact of the laser on dental caries. *Nature* 1964.
7. Kang Y, Rabie AB, Wong RW. A review of laser applications in orthodontics. *International journal of orthodontics (Milwaukee, Wis.)*. 2014 Jan 1;25(1):47-56.
8. Yamamoto H, Sato K. Prevention of dental caries by acousto-optically Q-switched Nd: YAG laser irradiation. *J Dent Res* 1980;59(2):137.
9. Myers TD, Myers ED, Stone RM. First soft tissue study utilizing a pulsed Nd:YAG dental laser. *Northwest Dent* 1989;68: 14-17.
10. Arjun Karra, Mohammadi Begum, "Lasers in orthodontics," *Int J Contemp Dent Med Rev*, vol. 2014, Article ID 041014, 2014.
11. Nelson DGA, Wefel JS, Jongebloed WL, Featherstone JDB. Morphology, Histology and Crystallography of Human Dental Enamel Treated with Pulsed Low-Energy Infrared Laser Radiation. *Caries Res*. 1987;21(5):411-26.
12. Visuri SR, Gilbert JL, Wright DD, Wigdor HA, Walsh JT. Shear Strength of Composite Bonded to Er:YAG Laser-prepared Dentin. *J Dent Res*. 1996 Jan;75(1):599-605.
13. Genovese MD, Olivi G. Use of laser technology in orthodontics: hard and soft tissue laser treatments. *Eur J Paediatr Dent*. 2010 Mar;11(1):44-8.
14. Kim J-H, Kwon O-W, Kim H-I, Kwon YH. Acid Resistance of Erbium-doped Yttrium Aluminum Garnet Laser-Treated and Phosphoric Acid-Etched Enamels. *The Angle Orthodontist*. 2006 Nov 1;76(6):1052-6.
15. Hamamcı N, Akkurt A, Başaran G. In vitro evaluation of microleakage under orthodontic brackets using two different laser etching, self etching and acid etching methods. *Lasers Med Sci*. 2010 Nov;25(6):811-6.
16. Noel L, Rebellato J, Sheats RD. The effect of argon laser irradiation on demineralization resistance of human enamel adjacent to orthodontic brackets: an in vitro study. *Angle Orthod* 2003 Jun;73(3):249-58.
17. Lee BS, Hsieh TT, Lee YL, Lan WH, Hsu YJ, Wen PH, et al. Bond strengths of orthodontic bracket after acid-etched, Er: YAG laser-irradiated and combined treatment on enamel surface. *Angle Orthod* 2003;73:565-70.
18. Ghafari J, Skanchy TL, Mante F. Shear bond strengths of two ceramic brackets. *J Clin Orthod*. 1992 Aug;26(8):491-3.
19. Bishara SE, Fonseca JM, Boyer DB. The use of debonding pliers in the removal of ceramic brackets: Force levels and enamel cracks. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 1995 Sep;108(3):242-8.

20. Tocchio RM, Williams PT, Mayer FJ, Standing KG. Laser debonding of ceramic orthodontic brackets. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 1993 Feb;103(2):155-62.
21. Oztoprak MO, Nalbantgil D, Erdem AS, Tozlu M, Arun T. Debonding of ceramic brackets by a new scanning laser method. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 2010 Aug;138(2):195-200.
22. Strobl K, Bahns TL, Wiliham L, Bishara SE, Stwalley WC. Laser-aided debonding of orthodontic ceramic brackets. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 1992 Feb;101(2):152-8.
23. Fernandes LM, B Ogaard B, Skoglund L. Pain and discomfort experienced after placement of a conventional or a superelastic NiTi aligning archwire: A randomized clinical trial. *J Orofac Orthop/Fortschr Kieferorthop*. 1998 Nov;59(6):331-9.
24. Walker J. Relief from chronic pain by low power laser irradiation. *Neuroscience Letters*. 1983 Dec;43(2-3):339-44.
25. Marini I, Gatto MR, Bonetti GA. Effects of Superpulsed Low-level Laser Therapy on Temporomandibular Joint Pain. *The Clinical Journal of Pain*. 2010 Sep;26(7):611-6.
26. Harazaki M, Isshiki Y. Soft laser irradiation effects on pain reduction in orthodontic treatment. *Bull Tokyo Dent Coll*. 1997 Nov;38(4):291-5.
27. Tortamano A, Lenzi DC, Haddad ACSS, Bottino MC, Dominguez GC, Vigorito JW. Low-level laser therapy for pain caused by placement of the first orthodontic archwire: A randomized clinical trial. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 2009 Nov;136(5):662-7.
28. Turhani D, Scheriau M, Kapral D, Benesch T, Jonke E, Bantleon HP. Pain relief by single low-level laser irradiation in orthodontic patients undergoing fixed appliance therapy. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 2006 Sep;130(3):371-7.
29. Lim H-M, Lew KKK, Tay DKL. A clinical investigation of the efficacy of low level laser therapy in reducing orthodontic postadjustment pain. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 1995 Dec;108(6):614-22.
30. van Breugel HHFI, Bär PRD. Power density and exposure time of He-Ne laser irradiation are more important than total energy dose in photo-biomodulation of human fibroblasts in vitro. *Lasers Surg Med*. 1992;12(5):528-37.
31. Poon VK, Huang L, Burd A. Biostimulation of dermal fibroblast by sublethal Q-switched Nd:YAG 532nm laser: Collagen remodeling and pigmentation. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology*. 2005 Oct;81(1):1-8.
32. Kawasaki K, Shimizu N. Effects of low-energy laser irradiation on bone remodeling during experimental tooth movement in rats. :10.

33. Cruz DR, Kohara EK, Ribeiro MS, Wetter NU. Effects of low-intensity laser therapy on the orthodontic movement velocity of human teeth: A preliminary study. *Lasers Surg Med.* 2004 Aug;35(2):117-20.
34. Goulart CS, Nouer PRA, Mouramartins L, Garbin IU, Lizarelli R de FZ. Photoradiation and Orthodontic Movement: Experimental Study with Canines. *Photomedicine and Laser Surgery.* 2006 Apr;24(2):192-6.
35. Angell EH. Treatment of irregularity of the permanent or adult teeth. *Dent Cosmos* 1860;1:540-4.
36. Haas AJ. The treatment of maxillary deficiency by opening the midpalatal suture. *Angle Orthod* 1965;35:200-17.
37. Hirose Y. Effects of low power laser to premaxillary suture during rapid expansion. *J Gifu Dent Soc* 1988;15:32-47. Saito S, Shimizu N. Stimulatory effects of low-power laser irradiation on bone regeneration in midpalatal suture during expansion in the rat. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop* 1997;111:525-32.
38. Angeletti P, Gomes HC, Ferreira LM. Effect of low-level laser therapy (GaAlAs) on bone regeneration in midpalatal anterior suture after surgically assisted rapid maxillary expansion. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod* 2010;109:38-46.
39. Santiago VC, Piram A, Fuziy A. Effect of soft laser in bone repair after expansion of the midpalatal suture in dogs. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2012 Nov;142(5):615-24.)
40. Anderson AM, Kao E, Gladwin M, Benli O, Ngan P. The effects of argon laser irradiation on enamel decalcification: An in vivo study. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics.* 2002 Sep;122(3):251-9.
41. Blankenau RJ, Powell GL, Ellis RW, Westerman GH. In Vivo Caries-Like Lesion Prevention with Argon Laser: Pilot Study. *Journal of Clinical Laser Medicine & Surgery.* 1999 Dec;17(6):241-3.
42. Oho T, Morioka T. A Possible Mechanism of Acquired Acid Resistance of Human Dental Enamel by Laser Irradiation. *Caries Res.* 1990;24(2):86-92.
43. Sarver DM, Yanosky M. Principles of cosmetic dentistry in orthodontics: Part 3. Laser treatments for tooth eruption and soft tissue problems. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics.* 2005 Feb;127(2):262-4.
44. Sarver DM, Yanosky M. Principles of cosmetic dentistry in orthodontics: Part 2. Soft tissue laser technology and cosmetic gingival contouring. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics.* 2005 Jan;127(1):85-90.
45. Miserendino LJ, Pick RM, Blankenau RJ. Laser safety in dental practice. In: Miserendino LJ, Pick RM, editors. *Lasers in Dentistry.* Singapore: Quintessence Publishing Co, Inc.; 1995. p. 85-103.